

From Tradition to Trend: A Case Study on Batik Reinvention through Innovation Diffusion Theory from Local Fashion Brands in Indonesia

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Abstract

This study examines the concept of reinvention of batik motifs in contemporary fashion trends in Indonesia through the perspective of innovation diffusion theory with a case study of two Indonesian fashion brands that use Batik for fashion design. This study uses a descriptive-qualitative approach with an analysis of interview results and creative strategies from both brands, which focus on adapting tradition to contemporary fashion trends. The findings of this study are: 1). reinvention of Batik is a dynamic process that simplifies traditional batik motifs adjusted to contemporary fashion trends; 2). There is a modification of production techniques and digitalization that adjusts to the conditions of brand resources; 3). There is a process of reinterpreting cultural values to those relevant to modern consumer preferences; 4). Strategic innovations implemented by both brands can maintain traditional values but remain relevant to contemporary fashion trends. This study emphasizes the role of designers as change agents in the diffusion of innovation and contributes to preserving traditional crafts in the ever-evolving fashion landscape.

Keywords: *Batik, Fashion, Reinvention, Trend.*

Suggested citation: Nursari, F., Mudra, I.W., Remawa, A.A.G.R., & Arumsari, A. (2025). From Tradition to Trend: A Case Study on Batik Reinvention through Innovation Diffusion Theory from Local Fashion Brands in Indonesia. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 65-72. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(3).06

Introduction

As one of the traditional textiles, Batik is a cultural heritage of the archipelago that is full of meaning and cultural values. All the elements that form Batik continuously inspire fashion designers in Indonesia to produce contemporary fashion designs relevant to the times' tastes. Batik is a collective work of art involving various hand skills in design and production. One form of the diffusion of batik innovation as a traditional textile is the shift in fashion styles that adopt Batik both as a motif and as a whole (Ratuannisa et al., 2020). The definition of Batik is holistically understood as a piece of cloth with various traditional decorations made using a resist dyeing technique (Doellah, 2002). One of the identities distinguishing other Batik from traditional Indonesian Batik is the use of wax as the primary material to resist color. In

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addition to wax being used as a barrier, decorations, and motifs on batik cloth in Indonesia are depicted using two main tools: canting and stamping.

Canting is a technique called batik tulis used to depict motifs on the surface of the cloth (Doellah, 2002). Copper stamps with traditional decorations are a more modern tool for depicting batik decorations on the surface of the cloth. Copper stamps are used to produce Batik, which is called stamped Batik. The combination of the two techniques, namely writing and stamping, is commonly done as a form of production efficiency and does not reduce the identity of the batik cloth as long as it is used as a barrier. Therefore, if a batik motif on the cloth is not made with the resist dyeing technique using wax, it is called a batik-patterned textile or imitation batik (Kudiya, 2019).

Technological innovation and developments have also influenced how Batik is produced and represented. Canting was used as a writing tool on the surface of batik cloth since the 17th century, and manual stamps in the 19th century were slowly replaced by more modern machine technology. This development resulted in modifications in color, composition, and stylization of motifs, thus enriching the visual dimension of batik motifs. One type of Batik known in Indonesia is coastal Batik, which has diverse and bold patterns. The coastal batik style is one example of a tradition-based textile whose visuals are greatly influenced by foreign nations' interaction on Java island, especially in coastal areas (Ishwara, Yahya, Moeis, & Rambe, 2011).

The pressure of the fashion industry and the demand for designs that are relevant to current trends are some of the factors that drive the transformation of the design and production process of traditional textiles such as Batik. Storytelling and visual reinterpretation of batik motifs by designers in contemporary fashion products can be seen as sustainable strategies because they consider the aspect of locality in visual communication (Basiroen, 2022). Technological developments, industry demands, and increasingly dynamic fashion trends are urgent to examine how the reinvention process occurs in the context of the theory of diffusion of innovation, which explains that the adoption of innovation is influenced by various factors such as relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. In the Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands, these factors were analyzed based on interview data to determine how Batik, a traditional textile, is adapted in the design and production realms to produce a new narrative without eliminating traditional values.

The innovation diffusion process is structurally parallel to fashion's trend formation and dissemination process. In the global fashion industry, Indonesian national identity shows cultural hybridity and representation strategies as part of fashion designers' adaptation and transformation of tradition-based textiles (Matsumoto, 2004). The reinterpretation of Batik in contemporary fashion includes visual aspects and is also part of a complex cultural construction in the Indonesian fashion industry (Royo, 2019). Therefore, designers act as early adopters and creators of meaning, who bring together new ideas with the needs of society and create trends as a result of the innovation diffusion process.

This study discusses how innovation spreads through technology adoption, the reinterpretation of aesthetics, and collaborative cultural engagement. The urgency of this study is the effort to develop the Indonesian fashion industry and creative economy that formulates tradition as an important resource in the aesthetic and innovative aspects of the contemporary fashion industry (Ningsih, 2022). Furthermore, Batik, as one of the tradition-based textiles, is a commodity that adapts to values, forms, and meanings in the contemporary fashion industry. This is due to the influence of globalization and the development of the creative industry in Indonesia (Hitchcock & Nuryanti, 2016). This study contributes to a broader conversation on the role of local knowledge systems and the importance of reinvention as a strategy for the sustainability of culture and tradition.

Literature Review

The theory used as the basis in this study refers to Everett M. Rogers' innovation diffusion theory as the leading theory and Eundok Kim's fashion trend theory to support it. Both theories are used systematically

to examine the spread of new ideas or innovations by placing designers as change agents in responding to social change, one of the factors that form trends. In the social and cultural scope, innovation in design is not only functional but can cause the diffusion of new values that form fashion trends. Diffusion is the process of spreading innovations that include new ideas or things through specific communication channels, such as mass media, social media, seminars, or direct discussions, which are carried out between individuals or groups in a social system over a specific period (Rogers, 2003). Communication is spreading innovation because parties share information to produce a common understanding. Based on this explanation, it can be understood that diffusion has four important elements: the existence of innovation and the communication process over time in a social system. Innovation can be interpreted as an idea, practice, or object considered new by society in a social system.

Innovation has several characteristics based on individual perceptions that help explain how quickly the innovation is adopted. The time dimension is an important element in the diffusion of innovation and can influence how innovation is introduced, accepted, or rejected by individuals or target communities. The innovation-decision process is when individuals gain initial knowledge about innovation, evaluate the information received, and decide to adopt or reject innovation. There are three different terms for adopting and implementing innovation: invention, innovation, and reinvention. Invention is the process of finding or creating new ideas. Innovation is the process of using ideas or creations. If new ideas and creations are not used, they cannot be called innovation. Therefore, it can be understood that innovation is the result of invention, while reinvention is a change from innovation caused by various social, economic, or environmental factors.

Reinvention is when users change or modify innovation when adopting and implementing it. This modification occurs because users adjust the innovation to their conditions or needs. In reinvention, innovation is not always adopted in its original form but can change and develop according to user needs. Ideally, innovation is flexible, adaptive, and dynamic so that it can be sustainable according to the relevance and needs of the target community. Reinvention can be measured by identifying elements in implementing innovation, including maintenance or standard and modification (Rogers, 2003). Furthermore, adopters tend to integrate innovation with norms, values, or environmental conditions to overcome differences that can be barriers to adoption. Based on this explanation, it is understood that innovation is not a fixed entity but constantly changes along with the times.

Materials and Methods

This study uses a qualitative-descriptive method based on two primary case studies: interviews with the Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands. Innovation from the Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands is one of the strategies for sustainable fashion design identified in previous research (Handayani, Hutama, and Sunarya, 2020). Meraki Studios is one of the Indonesian brands that practices a studio-based approach in artisanal fashion production to adapt to limited resources (Nursari, Febriani, & Utami, 2023). Collaboration between academics, communities, and artisans in the batik industry in Lasem, carried out by the Putrisavu brand, is a batik reinvention strategy that maintains the cultural meaning it represents (Ningsih, 2024). Furthermore, this is then able to provide space for design adaptation that is relevant to global fashion trends. Lasem hand-drawn batik is one of the traditional-based textiles developed by the Putrisavu brand through the reinvention of its batik motifs without eliminating the traditional aspect as its principal value so that it remains relevant to the tastes of the times and sustainable (Ningsih, 2024). The reinvention of Lasem hand-drawn batik aims to strengthen cultural diplomacy and increase the commercial value of these fashion products (Ningsih, 2024).

Both brands originate from Indonesia and often use motifs, techniques, or fabrics based on a tradition integrated with contemporary fashion design. The selection of these two brands for the case study was based on the identity of the brands that carry tradition and culture in designing contemporary fashion products. Data were collected through in-depth interviews regarding the creative processes of the two designers. Thematic analysis was conducted using Rogers' Diffusion of Innovation Theory framework to

identify patterns of reinvention and dissemination of traditional textile innovations into contemporary fashion. These criteria include the characteristics of innovation diffusion as explained by Rogers (2003) as follows:

1. Relative advantage is the extent to which an innovation is considered better than others, including comparisons with previous innovations. It can be measured based on economic, social, ease of use, and user satisfaction. Relative advantage does not need to be objectively assessed as superior as long as individuals or social groups view it as more useful.
2. Compatibility is the extent to which an innovation is consistent with societal norms, past experiences, and the needs of potential users. If the innovation communicated aligns with these three things, the tendency to be accepted will be greater. If the innovation is incompatible and requires changes to the value system or norms, the adoption process will be slower.
3. Complexity is how easily individuals or social groups can understand and use an innovation. Innovations that are easy to understand will be adopted more quickly. Conversely, if an innovation is considered difficult to understand, takes time to learn, creates new habits, or must change existing regulations, then the adoption process can be slower.
4. Trialability is the extent to which an innovation can be tested on a small scale before being adopted so that individuals or community groups can evaluate it before adopting it. If an innovation cannot be tested, it will raise doubts for individuals or community groups who are the targets of the innovation's dissemination. In this phase, innovators and change agents must generally have a plan to gradually socialize the innovation so that the target individuals or community groups can accept it.
5. Observability is the extent to which the results or benefits of an innovation can be seen, known, and observed by individuals or target groups. Visible results can trigger discussions between individuals in a social group, thus creating opportunities for adoption.

Additional attention is given to the reinvention process and the role of designers as agents of change in their respective communities. This is examined based on various backgrounds of the causes of reinvention, which can be sourced from the characteristics of the innovation, its adopters, or users. Innovations that are too complex and difficult to understand will tend to be modified (Rogers, 2003). The diffusion of innovation is closely related to the spread of fashion trends and their adoption rate in community groups. In addition to Rogers' diffusion of innovation theory, Eundok Kim's fashion trend theory is used as a complement to understand the reinvention of fashion brands towards traditional textiles such as Batik. A trend is an identifiable similarity across sources of information relating to style, details, or other aspects of appearance, characterized by increasing interest and awareness of that appearance (Kim et al., 2021). Change agents are individuals who have a primary role in influencing the decisions of innovation adopters and collaborating with opinion leaders to bridge the communication gap that commonly occurs with innovation adopters. Therefore, change agents need support from opinion leaders as innovators to help bridge the communication gap with innovation adopters. The task of change agents is not only to accelerate the diffusion of innovation but, under certain conditions, to prevent the diffusion of innovations that are not desired or not by the norms of a social system. Early Adopters, as change agents, want revolutionary change and want to be separated from the majority of consumers (Kim et al., 2021). Both innovators and early adopters tend to be opinion leaders.

Results and Discussion

The results and discussion of this study are reviewed and presented based on Rogers' (2003) innovation diffusion theory. The theory consists of five main characteristics: relative advantage compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability. In addition to the five characteristics of innovation diffusion, the role of designers as first responders who trigger diffusion as fashion trend makers is discussed. The role of designers is reviewed based on aspects that complement the study of innovation diffusion, namely the reinvention process and as change agents.

Relative Advantage

The relative advantage in this study refers to better or more optimal innovation in fashion design. Case studies of the two Indonesian fashion brands, namely Putrisavu and Meraki Studios, have symbolic and visual uniqueness because aspects of tradition and culture are integrated into the design of their fashion products. The Putrisavu brand has a relative advantage because it seeks to interpret innovation based on tradition and culture in the design aspect. Furthermore, this brand's production process still maintains the traditional batik technique, namely using a writing or stamp technique with wax as a barrier. This brand's primary target market focuses on people who understand and appreciate the meaning of tradition and culture in their fashion products. Therefore, aspects of tradition and local culture are strong values of Putrisavu's brand identity.

The relative advantage of the Meraki Studios brand is identified from the adaptation of motif designs and production techniques that are optimized but without eliminating the aspects of tradition and culture in the fashion products produced. The application of simplified motifs and modified production techniques can be done locally or by the surrounding community, while simultaneously highlighting the local aspects carried as the brand's identity. Simplification of motifs and production techniques is an effort to produce attractive motif visuals for the target market of the younger generation. There is an assumption that Batik is a textile with a conservative impression and symbolic meanings of colors and motifs bound by tradition. Innovation in the production process using block printing is carried out to replace the stamp and writing techniques commonly used in Batik, but wax is still used as a barrier. The Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands have different aspects of relative advantage even though both have innovations with local values that are carried. The innovations from these two brands have similar goals, namely to produce contemporary fashion products that have traditional values but are to current trends. Furthermore, the uniqueness that is the relative advantage of these two brands lies in their differences with the textiles used in mass-produced fast fashion.

Compatibility

Compatibility examines how innovation can be consistent with societal norms, past experiences, and user needs. Communication is an important aspect in assessing whether an innovation is compatible or not. In the case study of the Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands, compatibility is practiced by maintaining the meaning and tradition of batik motifs adapted to contemporary fashion clothing. In an interview, the designer of the Putrisavu brand explained the importance of considering the compatibility of innovation with cultural norms, philosophical meanings, and conventions or rules related to using batik techniques and motifs with strong traditional values, such as Batik. The rules or visual conventions that are the identity of the Batik are adapted with a comprehensive research background to maintain identity and ensure its compatibility with prevailing social norms. Meraki Studios has a different approach to adapting techniques and traditions as part of innovation compatibility. Batik techniques, which are oriented towards using wax as a barrier, are adapted with a similar concept but in a more straightforward and more relevant way to the studio's ability to utilize local resources for production. In addition to utilizing local resources in fashion production, there are modifications to block printing and digitalization in several aspects of design and production that were initially done manually. The innovation compatibility of the Meraki Studios brand can be seen from the stylization of visually more modern and minimalist motifs so that they are more relevant to a broader target market without worrying about inconsistencies with specific traditional rules.

Complexity and Trialability

Complexity examines how innovation can be understood and utilized by individuals or groups and is related to trialability, where the complexity of innovation affects its ability to be tested and understood so that individuals or groups of people can evaluate it before adopting it. Therefore, complexity and trialability are important aspects of contemporary fashion design for the Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands. In terms of complexity, the Putrisavu brand avoids using overly complex traditional textiles in their entirety. This is part of the design considerations to ensure the suitability of the fabric for the

clothing to be produced. The solution taken by the brand is to carry out a visual interpretation of the visual elements of the textile. Related to the trialability aspect, the Putrisavu brand uses a problem-based approach and observes global trends to assess whether the inspiration raised has relevance to market tastes. The problem-based approach is used first to understand the characteristics of traditional-based textiles used in the design so that they can be used optimally and by the rules or values of the tradition they represent.

The Meraki Studios brand uses a studio-based approach related to trialability. This approach allows Meraki Studios designers to experiment with innovations, including techniques or materials. The trials or experiments are low-risk because they are carried out on a small scale with simplified methods according to the capabilities of production resources. This brand anticipates complexity by selecting sustainable techniques, such as screen printing and block printing, so it does not need to rely entirely on professional artisans. This choice allows the brand to make the production process efficient regarding time, costs, and energy required. Applying problem-based and studio-based methods allows both brands to adjust designs with actual consumer feedback but with minimal risk and remain flexible in the design process.

Observability

Observability refers to the extent to which an innovation is visible to a target group or community that can trigger opportunities for evaluation and adoption. In this case, both Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands use social media and storytelling to increase observability to the target market. Both brands communicate how contemporary fashion integrates with tradition and culture, one of which is related to Batik. The Meraki Studios brand added that imperfections in their designs can provide unique aesthetic value. The brand also highlights the observability aspect through an educational communication strategy on social media by creating storytelling that educates consumers that imperfections in manual printing are part of the artistic value and uniqueness of the product. The strategy to increase observability by the Putrisavu brand differs from Meraki Studios in terms of content that is educated to the target market. Putrisavu's storytelling focuses on the traditional and cultural values of each contemporary fashion product produced, including listing the names of the artisans and the area of origin of the textiles used. In addition to increasing observability, this also strengthens the credibility of fashion products, making innovation easy for the target market to observe.

Reinvention

Reinvention in the Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands covers how innovation is changed or modified by the brand as a user when implementing it in the design process. Both modifications are different because they adjust to each brand's environmental conditions, resources, and needs. Reinvention is a strategy to maintain the relevance of aspects of tradition and culture in contemporary fashion product design. The Putrisavu brand maintains the philosophical meaning of traditional textiles' tangible and intangible aspects but with innovation in their form and function. This brand maintains the philosophical meaning of traditional textiles, although it modifies the form, function, and type of textiles used to be relevant to current tastes. Furthermore, this brand prioritizes using local human and natural resources without reducing its products' identity and aesthetic value.

The reinvention of the Meraki Studios brand consists of visual stylization and experimental motif composition, especially in block printing techniques. One form of reinvention is using block printing techniques from copper stamps identical to Batik. In addition to block printing techniques, the use of screen printing techniques and digital printing is part of simplifying the visual form of Batik without removing its basic elements.

Innovation Decision Process

The time dimension is an important aspect of the innovation-decision process. It includes the time required for the brand to learn about the innovation, evaluate the information, and decide to adopt or reject it. The Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands make continuous improvements that are flexible and informal in the form of trials and feedback. Furthermore, the Putrisavu brand adapts to the alignment with the traditions and feedback of the target market, while Meraki Studios focuses on studio-scale

exploration. These processes are part of the innovation-decision process to perfect the product before producing it on a larger scale.

Figure 1. Batik Lasem Designed by Putrisavu

Figure 2. Contemporary Batik Designed by Meraki Studios

Fashion Change Agents and Opinion Leaders

The Putrisavu and Meraki Studios brands have a role in the Indonesian fashion industry as fashion change agents and build initial opinions. Putrisavu as a brand raises collaboration between designers, artisans, academics, and communities. This brand prioritizes a participatory approach to artisans in the design process to obtain a collective understanding of the innovations being developed. Furthermore, Meraki Studios is one of the Indonesian fashion brands that uses a studio-based approach as a design and production process on a small scale that is explorative and underlines the role of the Meraki Studios brand as a fashion change agent because it uses an unconventional approach.

Conclusion

This study provides an understanding that the reinvention of Batik as a traditional textile in contemporary fashion design is an adaptive strategy relevant to the tastes of the times, especially in maintaining cultural

values. The approach taken with the innovation diffusion theory and fashion trends on the Putrisavu and Meraki Studios fashion brands shows five main characteristics of innovation diffusion in the design process. The Putrisavu brand prioritizes philosophical aspects and traditional values through storytelling and collaboration with local artisans. This approach differs from Meraki Studios, which focuses on visual exploration and efficiency of production techniques such as digital technology and block print modifications. However, both adopted a reinvention strategy to adjust the design and production techniques of Batik to contemporary fashion trends while still maintaining the traditional values of Batik. The innovation-decision process in the Putrisavu and Meraki studio brands is adaptive, with studio-scale trials or relying on consumer feedback. This flexibility allows the brand to remain sustainable in developing contemporary fashion trends. Designers from both brands act as fashion change agents and initiate and educate artisans and target markets about the cultural values in their fashion products. Both opinion leaders also involve local communities as pioneers in transforming traditional textiles, such as Batik, into an inclusive, adaptive, and sustainable fashion industry. This study emphasizes the importance of collaboration in aspects of technological innovation, culture, and communication strategies in developing fashion products with traditional textiles. Furthermore, designers from both brands become drivers of the innovation diffusion process in the context of integrating tradition with contemporary fashion trends.

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